

ENERGISE

EUROPEAN NETWORK FOR RESEARCH, GOOD PRACTICE
AND INNOVATION FOR SUSTAINABLE ENERGY

EUROPEAN POLICY BRIEF

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WP2 REPORT SUMMARISING HIGH LEVEL FINDINGS ACROSS COUNTRIES

POLICY BRIEF AND RECOMMENDATIONS

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SECIS AND THEIR PROBLEM FRAMINGS

ENERGISE has reviewed and assessed 1000+ European Sustainable Energy Consumption Initiatives (SECIs), which has resulted in a public database that can be found on <http://energise-project.eu/projects>.

The database gives the viewer access to reading about the assessed SECIs according to descriptions, goals and objectives. The SECIs are shown in relation to national affiliation and categorized in terms of scale. Each SECI has been typologized according to the Problem Framing Typology (which is detailed in Jensen (2017) and Jensen et al (2018)).

The typologized SECIs suggest an overreliance on problem framing and related approaches that assume changes in energy demand and energy use to be a result of technological change or changes in individual behaviours. In compiling the database, researchers were primarily looking for initiatives that include socio-technical or practice-based elements (i.e. initiatives that are not purely technology focused). Therefore the number of sustainable energy initiatives that have a strong technological focus is presumably much greater than what is represented here.

The table below highlights the 4 categories in the ENERGISE Problem Framing Typology, the description of each type of problem framing, the objectives as part of each problem framing and finally the share of assessed SECIs that can be subsumed under each category.

Category	Description	Example	Number of assessed SEICs within this category
<p>Changes in technology</p>	<p>This problem framing assumes that changing levels in energy use is a matter of technological change and optimization</p>	<p>Optimizing existing products so they become more energy efficient; technical innovation; focusing on large-scale technical changes from fossil fuel to renewable energy</p>	<p>282 SEICs out of a total of 1067</p>
<p>Changes in individual behaviour</p>	<p>This problem framing assumes that changing levels of energy use is a matter of changing individuals' behaviour in terms their (personal) energy use, and their attitudes and choices related to energy efficiency</p>	<p>Information campaigns or nudging approaches that seeks to convince the individual about rational use of energy, or to adopt more energy <i>efficient</i> lifestyles.</p>	<p>514 SEICs out of a total of 1067</p>
<p>Changes in everyday life situations</p>	<p>This problem framing assumes that changing levels of energy use is a matter of changing material components, images/norms and competences related to specific areas of daily life. Tends to include elements of energy sufficiency.</p>	<p>Understanding, challenging, engaging with and enabling (new) meanings, skills and material arrangements related to various everyday life situations. These can be connected to practices such as cooking and showering.</p>	<p>124 SEICs out of a total of 1067</p>
<p>Changes in complex interactions</p>	<p>This problem framing assumes that changing levels of energy use is a matter of changing complex interactions between several areas of household related activities, professions and sectors. Occasionally, initiatives underpinned by this problem framing builds on notions of energy sufficiency. This includes assuming that 'social organization' is the key target for change, and that water, heat and energy consumption happens because of certain ways of organizing daily life across domains, sectors and practices.</p>	<p>Targeting systems of energy provision, configurations of energy demand, including various actors involved in (re) procuring certain dynamics of existing or new systems of production and consumption.</p>	<p>147 SEICs out of a total of 1067</p>

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

- ENERGISE recommends learning from SECIs that are subsumed under categories “Changes in everyday life situations” and “Changes in complex interactions”
- ENERGISE Living Labs can be regarded initiatives that can be subsumed across those categories.

References:

Jensen (2017) *Identification of key success factors and related indicators*. ENERGISE – European Network for Research, Good Practice and Innovation for Sustainable Energy, Grant Agreement No. 727642, Deliverable 2.2.

Jensen, C., Goggins, G., Fahy, F., Grealis, E., Vadovics, E., Genus, A., Rau, H (2018). Towards a practice-theoretical classification of sustainable energy consumption initiatives: Insights from social scientific energy research in 30 European countries. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 45: 297-306.

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“RESEARCH FOR SOCIETY”

ENERGISE invites you to join the online consultation ‘Research for Society’. Together with a variety of other actors from 30 European countries you will evaluate and enrich proposed research programmes that will be further explored as research topics and policy options.

Visit our website at: www.energise-project.eu

WHO WE ARE

The ENERGISE consortium includes ten research partners (universities, research institutes, enterprises and NGOs) from Bulgaria, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Slovenia, Switzerland, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom.

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